

Ionic Reactions in Thionyl Chloride. Part III. Nature of Thionyl Chloride in certain Acid-base Complexes of Pyridine

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Studies on molar conductance of the complexes, $(C_5H_5N)_2MCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$ (M is tin or titanium) and $(C_5H_5N)_2SnCl_4$ in nitrobenzene indicate that the former class behaves as uni-univalent electrolytes and constitution of these may be suggested as $(C_5H_5NSOCl)^+(C_5H_5NMCl_3)^-$ which does not violate hexa-covalency of tin or titanium. The addition of thionyl chloride to the nitrobenzene solutions of all the three complexes converts them into uni-bivalent electrolytes since chloride ion, being a strong nucleophile, displaces pyridine. On the basis of available evidence, mechanism for nucleophilic substitution in these complexes may be suggested to involve S_N1 course for tin complexes and S_N2 course for the titanium complex.

Although thionyl chloride has been undoubtedly shown to be a polar solvent by most of the conventional techniques¹⁻⁶, there are still certain intriguing problems which need elucidation. In the previous study⁵, it has been reported that solvo-bases, viz., pyridine, quinoline, and isoquinoline, react with solvo-acids, such as titanium tetrachloride, stannic chloride, and zirconium tetrachloride, to form solid compounds of the general formula, $B_2MCl_4 \cdot xSOCl_2$ (B stands for a molecule of the base, M for metal atoms and x varies from zero to one, depending on the nature of the base). The presence of solvent molecule in these complexes, which is due to partial desolvation and nature of the linkage,⁵ has not been investigated.

The main object of the present investigation has been to ascertain the role of thionyl chloride in partially and completely desolvated complexes. In partially desolvated complexes, the assignment of co-ordination number, stereochemistry, and nature of linkage would be useful in satisfying constitutional requirements. Since the study of acid-base neutralisation reactions in thionyl chloride by conductometric method²⁻³ provides ample evidence in support of the formation of complexes $(BSOCl)_2^+(MCl_6)^{2-}$ and $(BSOCl)^+(SOCl)^-(MCl_6)^{2-}$ entailing ionisation of thionyl chloride, it is of interest to carry out conductance measurements in nitrobenzene which is not a self-ionising solvent. A study of molar conductance of thionyl chloride, pyridine, and stannic chloride in nitrobenzene solutions showed that thionyl chloride and pyridine did not affect the conductance of nitrobenzene, indicating thereby their almost nonelectrolyte nature. Dimethylphenylbenzylammonium bromide behaves as a uni-univalent electrolyte, which is in accordance with its accepted constitution. The molar conductance of stannic chloride in nitrobenzene, when plotted against time,

Presented at the 2nd Annual Convention of the Indian Chemical Society at Allahabad, December 1964.

1. Pease and Luder, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 5195.
2. Spandau and Brunneck, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1955, **278**, 197.
3. Sandhu *et al.*, *this Journal*, 1960, **37**, 329.
4. Masters *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 4252.
5. Sandhu, *this Journal*, 1962, **39**, 589.
6. Sandhu *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1959, **36**, 305.

shows, however, an increase in its value and reaches the maximum value of 17.3 after an interval of 24 hr. The measured values of molar conductance of the compounds, considered in this investigation, are recorded in Table I.

TABLE I

Compound.	Molar conduc. at 30°.	Conc.
SnCl ₄	17.30	0.398 m M/l
[(CH ₃) ₂ NH ₅ C ₇ H ₇]Br	23.30	0.540
(C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂ . SnCl ₄ . SOCl ₂	25.50	0.320
(C ₅ H ₅ N) ₂ . TiCl ₄ . SOCl ₂	22.16	0.243

The conductance of boron tribromide in nitrobenzene has been explained on the basis of following equilibria⁷:

Tin in stannic chloride has a strong tendency to increase its co-ordination number to 6 because of the availability of outer *d*-orbitals. Thus an interaction of stannic chloride and nitrobenzene may result in the establishment of the following equilibria:

Since the molar conductance at the steady state does not exceed the required value for a uni-univalent electrolyte, the possibility for the existence of equilibrium (v) is relatively small as compared to (iii) and (iv); among these, (iii) may again be predominant because of poor donor capacity of nitrobenzene.

The complex (C₅H₅N)₂ SnCl₄ is a nonelectrolyte in nitrobenzene solution and it indicates that nitrobenzene does not solvate this complex since it is a poor nucleophile with respect to chloride ion and pyridine.

The molar conductance of partially desolvated complexes (C₅H₅N)₂MCl₄. SOCl₂ (M = Sn or Ti) in nitrobenzene solution also increases with time and the constant values, obtained after an interval of 24 hours, are 25.5 and 22.16, as shown in Table I. It is apparent that the molar conductance of these complexes corresponds to that of uni-univalent electrolytes in nitrobenzene. Thus the constitution of these complexes may be proposed as (C₅H₅N. SOCl)⁺ (C₅H₅N.MCl₃)⁻, which maintains hexa-co-ordination of the central metal atom (Fig. 2).

Thionyl chloride, which is initially a nonelectrolyte in nitrobenzene, manifests interesting features when it is added to the solutions of partially or completely desolvated complexes

in nitrobenzene. The dropwise addition of thionyl chloride to the solution of completely desolvated complex, $(C_5H_5N)_2SnCl_4$, enhances its molar conductance considerably and the

FIG. 1. Effect of thionyl chloride on the solutions of complexes.

equilibrium in favour of their formation. The co-ordination number of metal remains 6 and the mechanism shown in chart I is suggested for the change of covalent species into ionic species.

In the case of titanium complex, the transition state may involve seven-covalent species as indicated in pathway (a). This assumption is based on the fact that titanium has got vacant $3d$ orbitals which have favourable energy for an increase of co-ordination number to 7. Literature records evidence in favour of eight-co-ordinated complexes of titanium as proved by X-ray diffraction⁹. Thus S_N2 course is anticipated for titanium complexes. The pathway (b) shown for tin, however, involves five-covalent species and the

results are plotted in Fig. 1. The excessive amount of thionyl chloride has no further appreciable effect on molar conductance of the complex when the value of 51.3 is reached, corresponding to univalent electrolytes. Similar increase in molar conductance of partially desolvated complexes $(C_5H_5N)_2SnCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$ and $(C_5H_5N)_2TiCl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$ in nitrobenzene with the addition of thionyl chloride is recorded in Fig. 1.

The mechanism for this increase in the molar conductance of the aforementioned complexes in presence of thionyl chloride appears to be substitution on metal centre. The chloride ion, which is a fairly strong nucleophile, attacks the metal centre in the complex and displaces pyridine which readily picks up thionylum ion to form $C_5H_5N^+ \cdot SOCl_2$. Thionyl chloride, which is a nonelectrolyte in nitrobenzene, because of its inherent polar nature acts as a potential source of chloride ions which are sufficient to influence the

9. Clark *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 2460.

dence in favour of five-covalency of tin is available in literature⁹⁻¹². The existence of intermediate species $(\text{BMCl}_5)^-$ is corroborated by the molar conductance data of the partially desolvated complexes. Thus increase in molar conductance of these complexes in nitrobenzene with the addition of thionyl chloride is explained, whereas addition of pyridine does not affect their molar conductance.

CHART I

The two-pathways for substitution mechanism.

 9. Clark *et al.*, *Proc. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 85.

 10. Beattie *et al.*, *Chem. & Ind.*, 1962, 1429.

 11. Kerk *et al.*, *Chimia*, 1962, 16, 10.

 12. Beattie and Gilson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2585.

FIG. 2. Effect of time on the solution of $(C_5H_5N)_2 Sn Cl_4 \cdot SOCl_2$ in nitrobenzene.

EXPERIMENTAL

Nitrobenzene (commercial grade) was steam-distilled after addition of H_2SO_4 (dil.) and the distillate was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride. On redistillation, the fraction boiling at $209-10^\circ$ was collected. Thionyl chloride was purified as described earlier⁶ and all the complexes were prepared, as reported previously³, with the exception of $(C_5H_5N)_2 SnCl_4$.

The compound $(C_5H_5N)_2 SnCl_4$ was prepared by allowing chilled solution of stannic chloride (3.05 g.) to react with pyridine (1.85 g.) in the molar ratio of 1:2, both in dry and purified CCl_4 . The white complex was filtered through a sintered glass funnel and kept in a special assembly, avoiding contact with moisture. Tin was weighed as tin dioxide and chlorine was estimated by Volhard's method. (Found: Cl, 34.64, 34.42; Sn, 28.11, 28.82. Calc.: Cl, 34.97; Sn, 28.23%).

Conductance measurements were carried out by using Philips conductivity bridge and precision measuring bridge, type WBR, No. 108 with logarithmic indicator amplifier, type TAV, IKC, No. 034, manufactured by Wissenschaftlich Technische Werkstätten, Weilheim /Oby, Germany.